

Beamspace and Frequency Domain ISAC Resource Allocation using Reinforcement Learning

Petteri Pulkkinen^{*†}, Majdoddin Esfandiari^{*}, and Visa Koivunen^{*}

^{*}Department of Information and Communications Engineering, Aalto University, Espoo, Finland

[†]Saab Finland Oy, Helsinki, Finland

Email: petteri.pulkkinen@aalto.fi, majdoddin.esfandiari@aalto.fi, visa.koivunen@aalto.fi

Abstract—In the emerging 6G systems, joint sensing and communications require efficient spatial and frequency domain waveform design and resource allocation to meet system performance objectives. Traditional structured optimization algorithms often face practical challenges such as non-convexity, high computational demand, lack of adaptability, and significant performance degradation when the assumed model is invalid or dynamic. Reinforcement learning (RL) offers a data-driven alternative that leverages observed data to overcome these deficits. This paper combines RL principles with acquired model awareness of radio environment dynamics, thereby enhancing the learning data efficiency and making the algorithm more interpretable than traditional model-free RL methods. We introduce an RL algorithm based on Thompson sampling for allocating subcarriers and beams in the beamspace domain to achieve desired performance levels in wireless communications and radar sensing tasks. The proposed RL method effectively learns from its experiences and balances sensing and communications functionalities, achieving superior target detection performance and competitive communication rates compared to traditional methods.

Index Terms—Integrated sensing and communications (ISAC), reinforcement learning (RL), Thompson sampling, spatial resource optimization, frequency resource allocation

I. INTRODUCTION

There is an ongoing convergence of wireless communications and radio frequency (RF) sensing technologies [1]. Current 5G and emerging 6G wireless systems utilize multicarrier waveforms and large aperture antenna arrays to ensure high-quality service in dense spectrum environments. Similarly, modern fully adaptive radars employ large antenna apertures capable of simultaneously launching multiple waveforms and broadband signaling [2]. In integrated sensing and communications (ISAC) systems, radar and communications hardware and waveforms are co-designed and jointly optimized for mutual benefits. However, this integration presents significant technical challenges, particularly in effectively allocating spatial and frequency resources to satisfy the performance requirements and trading off among different sensing and communications objectives.

This paper develops model-based reinforcement learning (RL) methods for spatial and frequency resource allocation and waveform optimization in multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) Orthogonal Frequency-Division Multiplexing (OFDM) ISAC systems. Structured optimization methods for single-input single-output (SISO) multicarrier systems have been considered, for example, in [3]–[7]. For single carrier MIMO

ISAC systems, optimization methods for transmit beamforming have been developed in [8], [9]. Furthermore, optimization methods for MIMO OFDM systems have been proposed in [10]–[15]. These methods are developed for fully digital [10]–[12] or hybrid analog-digital [13]–[15] transceiver architectures. Furthermore, the sensing performance objectives are based on mutual information (MI) [10], Cramér–Rao bound (CRB) [15], probability of detection (PoD) [11], or achieving the desired beam pattern [12], [14]. Typically, either the sensing objective [11], [15] is maximized subject to rate constraints for each user, or the sum-rate is maximized under sensing constraints [14]. However, [10] considers the weighted sum among the sensing and communications objectives, and [12] uses the multi-objective optimization approach to achieve a Pareto-optimal solution.

The structured optimization methods considered above assume that all model parameters are known or reliably estimated and may employ high-complexity algorithms unsuitable for highly dynamic radio environments. This may not be feasible in dynamic propagation, target, and spectrum environments where adaptation and learning from past experiences are vital [16]. RL methods [17] learn from the observed data to address modeling deficits and autonomously improve performance by learning from experiences. Hence, they provide a promising technology for ISAC systems that are subject to modeling deficits and operate in highly dynamic radio environments.

This paper proposes a RL approach, realizing a closed-loop cognitive ISAC system. The cognitive radar [2] refers to fully adaptive radar systems capable of learning by executing a Sense-Learn-Adapt (SLA) cognitive cycle and making decisions based on closed-loop feedback. In our earlier work [18], we developed RL methods within the multi-armed bandit (MAB) framework [19] that use a beamspace domain design [20] to provide an orthogonal model for ISAC resource allocation tasks in the spatial domain. In this paper, we propose an RL method that allocates resources in spatial (beamspace) and frequency (subcarrier or resource block (RB)) domains simultaneously to achieve the desired performance in sensing and communications tasks in ISAC while adapting to changes in the operational radio environment. We demonstrate that the proposed closed-loop approach improves target detection performance and maintains competitive communication rates, making it a promising method for cognitive ISAC systems.

II. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

Consider MIMO OFDM ISAC system serving K single antenna user equipments (UEs) and in the presence of Q radar targets with a priori unknown locations. We consider a monostatic OFDM sensing model where it is assumed that base station (BS) can transmit and receive signals simultaneously [21]. The BS is equipped with uniform linear array (ULA) of L_R receive and L_T transmit antennas. The receive and transmit array steering vectors are defined as $\mathbf{u}_R(\theta) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{L_R}}[1, e^{-j\pi \sin(\theta)}, \dots, e^{-j\pi(L_R-1)\sin(\theta)}]^T$ and $\mathbf{u}_T(\theta) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{L_T}}[1, e^{-j\pi \sin(\theta)}, \dots, e^{-j\pi(L_T-1)\sin(\theta)}]^T$, respectively. We use downlink communication signals for sensing purposes in addition to dedicated sensing signals.

A. Transmit signal model

Consider MIMO-OFDM signal with a sub-carrier spacing of Δf and a symbol interval of $T_o = T_{cp} + \frac{1}{\Delta f}$, where T_{cp} is the cyclic prefix (CP) duration. Each OFDM frame comprises N sub-carriers and M OFDM symbols. The considered ISAC transmit signal can be written as

$$\mathbf{x}_{n,m} = \sum_{k=0}^K \mathbf{x}_{n,m}^{(k)} \quad (1)$$

where $n = 1, \dots, N$ and $m = 1, \dots, M$ refer to the sub-carrier index and the OFDM symbol index, respectively. In addition, $\mathbf{x}_{n,m}^{(k)}$ for $k = 1, \dots, K$ are the signals transmitted to UEs and $k = 0$ refers to the signal component dedicated to the sensing function. Denote $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M \times L_T}$ as the tensor comprising all signal vectors of equation (1). Define matrix $\mathbf{U} \in \mathbb{C}^{L_T \times L}$, an arbitrary codebook matrix associated with L beams. For example, \mathbf{U} can be the discrete Fourier transform (DFT) matrix of size $L_T \times L_T$ such that we have $L = L_T$ orthogonal beams. Using the beamspace basis, the signal components for $k = 0, \dots, K$ are defined as

$$\mathbf{x}_{n,m}^{(k)} = \mathbf{U} \mathbf{\Lambda}_n^{(k)} \mathbf{c}_{n,m}^{(k)} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{\Lambda}_n^{(k)} \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times L}$ is a diagonal matrix, and the vector $\mathbf{c}_{n,m}^{(k)} \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times 1}$ comprises the data symbols for L spatially multiplexed data streams. The covariance matrix of vector $\mathbf{c}_{n,m}^{(k)}$ is an identity matrix \mathbf{I}_L of size L . Also, the symbols are assumed to be independent among the indexes n and m . In the case of single antenna UEs, only one data stream is transmitted for each user such that matrix $\mathbf{W}_n^{(k)} = \mathbf{U} \mathbf{\Lambda}_n^{(k)}$ for all $k \geq 1$ typically boils down to a beamforming vector.¹ However, we can transmit as many waveforms as needed for sensing-only purposes such that there are no constraints on the number of non-zero columns for the matrix $\mathbf{W}_n^{(0)} = \mathbf{U} \mathbf{\Lambda}_n^{(0)}$. We will show that this more general transmit signal model in (2) is useful for all k (even in the single stream) case when optimizing the performance of the ISAC system.

¹This constraint comes from the method used to encode and decode the communications data.

B. Sensing receive signal model

We consider a point target model for Q targets. Thus, the received signal reflected off the targets can be written as²

$$\mathbf{y}_{n,m} = \sum_{q=1}^Q \alpha_q e^{j2\pi(m\rho_q T_o - n\Delta f \tau_q)} \mathbf{u}_R(\theta_q) \mathbf{u}_T^H(\theta_q) \mathbf{x}_{n,m} + \mathbf{v}_{n,m} \quad (3)$$

where α_q is the target scattering coefficient (including RCS, path loss, and other losses), τ_q is the two-way propagation delay, ρ_q is the Doppler frequency, θ_q is the azimuth angle, and noise $\mathbf{v}_{n,m} \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \sigma^2 \mathbf{I}_{L_R})$ is assumed to obey zero-mean circular complex Gaussian distribution with covariance matrix $\sigma^2 \mathbf{I}_{L_R}$. We also assume that the noise is independent between N subcarriers and M symbols. The target scattering coefficient $\alpha_q \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_{\alpha_q}^2)$ for all Q targets is assumed to be zero mean complex Gaussian distributed with variance $\sigma_{\alpha_q}^2$ (later target gain), corresponding to the Swerling I model. Furthermore, α_q is assumed to be independent between the targets.

The sensing subsystem performs a detection task using a generalized likelihood ratio test (GLRT) detector where the nuisance parameters are the target parameters α , τ , ρ , and θ . Specifically, we use the maximum likelihood method to estimate α in closed-form and plug it into the likelihood ratio test. This test statistic can be evaluated in a 3D grid of points for τ , ρ , and θ . Thus, the test statistic is

$$\eta(\tau, \rho, \theta) = \frac{1}{\sigma^2 C(\theta; \mathbf{X})} |S(\tau, \rho, \theta; \mathbf{X})|^2 \quad (4)$$

where

$$S(\tau, \rho, \theta; \mathbf{X}) = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^M e^{j2\pi(m\rho T_o - n\Delta f \tau)} \mathbf{y}_{n,m}^H \mathbf{u}_R(\theta) \mathbf{u}_T^H(\theta) \mathbf{x}_{n,m} \quad (5)$$

and

$$C(\theta; \mathbf{X}) = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^M |\mathbf{u}_T^H(\theta) \mathbf{x}_{n,m}|^2. \quad (6)$$

The function $S(\tau, \rho, \theta; \mathbf{X})$ can be interpreted as the matched filter, and $C(\theta; \mathbf{X})$ is the beamspace of the transmit waveform.

The distributions under null hypothesis \mathcal{H}_0 (target not present) and alternative hypothesis \mathcal{H}_1 (target present) are

$$\eta(\tau, \rho, \theta) | \mathcal{H}_0 \sim \mathcal{E}(\eta; 1) \quad (7a)$$

$$\eta(\tau, \rho, \theta) | \mathcal{H}_1 \sim \mathcal{E}\left(\eta; C(\theta; \mathbf{X}) \frac{\sigma_{\alpha}^2}{\sigma^2} + 1\right) \quad (7b)$$

where $\mathcal{E}(\eta; \mu) = \mu^{-1} e^{-\frac{\eta}{\mu}}$ is the probability density function (PDF) of exponential distribution with the mean of $\mu > 0$. The equation (7a) facilitates constant false alarm rate (CFAR) property of the GLRT detector.

²Without loss of generality, the elevation angle is left out to simplify the notation.

For specific target parameters of τ , ρ and θ , the detector decides target presence by

$$z(\tau, \rho, \theta) = \mathbb{1}_{\{\eta(\tau, \rho, \theta) \geq -\ln P_{\text{fa}}\}} \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbb{1}_{\{\cdot\}}$ is an indicator function, P_{fa} is the probability of false alarm, and $z(\tau, \rho, \theta) = 1$ refers to a decision that the target with the associated parameters is present. The PoD of a target can be written as

$$P_{\text{d}}(\theta, \sigma_{\alpha}^2; \mathbf{X}) = P_{\text{fa}}^{\left(C(\theta; \mathbf{X}) \frac{\sigma_{\alpha}^2}{\sigma_{\text{d}}^2} + 1\right)^{-1}} \quad (9)$$

which depends on factors such as the target azimuth angle, variance of the scattering coefficient, and the transmitted waveform.

C. Communications signal model

The received communications signal at UE $k = 1, \dots, K$ can be written as

$$r_{n,m}^{(k)} = \underbrace{(\mathbf{h}_n^{(k)})^{\text{H}} \mathbf{x}_{n,m}^{(k)}}_{\text{signal of interest}} + \overbrace{\sum_{k' \neq k} (\mathbf{h}_n^{(k)})^{\text{H}} \mathbf{x}_{n,m}^{(k')}}^{\text{interference}} + \underbrace{v_{n,m}^{(k)}}_{\text{noise}} \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{h}_n^{(k)}$ is the communications channel to user k on sub-carrier n , and $v_{n,m}^{(k)} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_k^2)$ is the zero-mean complex Gaussian noise with variance σ_k^2 . The codebook matrix \mathbf{U} in (2) applies the beamspace transform on the communications channel such that $(\mathbf{h}_n^{(k)})^{\text{H}} \mathbf{x}_{n,m}^{(k')} = (\bar{\mathbf{h}}_n^{(k)})^{\text{H}} \mathbf{\Lambda}_n^{(k')} \mathbf{c}_{n,m}^{(k')}$ where $\bar{\mathbf{h}}_n^{(k)} = \mathbf{U}^{\text{H}} \mathbf{h}_n^{(k)}$. Note we assume a block-fading model for the communications channel such that the channel remains approximately constant over M OFDM symbols but can vary between the blocks.

Define $g_{n,l}^{(k)} := [|\bar{\mathbf{h}}_n^{(k)}|^2]_l$ and $p_{n,l}^{(k)} = [\mathbf{\Lambda}_n^{(k)} (\mathbf{\Lambda}_n^{(k)})^{\text{H}}]_{l,l}$ that are respectively the gain and power on user k , sub-carrier n , and beam l . Furthermore, the tensors $\mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times M \times L}$ and $\mathbf{P} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times M \times L}$ comprise all the gain and power values, respectively. With the assumed model, the communications rate for user k is bounded from above by

$$\mathcal{R}_k(\mathbf{G}; \mathbf{P}) = \frac{1}{T_{\text{o}}} \sum_{n=1}^N \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\sum_{l=1}^L g_{n,l}^{(k)} p_{n,l}^{(k)}}{\sum_{k' \neq k} \sum_{l=1}^L g_{n,l}^{(k')} p_{n,l}^{(k')} + \sigma_k^2} \right) \quad (11)$$

where $1/T_{\text{o}} = \Delta f$ if $T_{\text{cp}} = 0$.

D. Resource allocation problem

We consider a joint allocation of beam and frequency resources in MIMO OFDM ISAC systems. The task is to obtain as many correct detections of the targets as possible while simultaneously serving UEs with an acceptable rate. The problem can be written as a constrained regret [19] minimization problem

$$\arg \min_{\pi} \sum_{t=1}^T \mu_t - |\mathcal{D}_t| \quad (12a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \mathcal{R}_k(\mathbf{G}_t; \mathbf{P}_t) \geq C_k \quad \forall k = 1, \dots, K \quad (12b)$$

where $|\mathcal{D}_t|$ is the number of true positives (successful detections associated with true targets), and $\mu_t \leq Q$ is the optimal expected number of true positives at time instants $t = 1, \dots, T$ where T is the evaluation horizon. Note this objective is defined under the CFAR property of the GLRT detector. This problem is a non-trivial partially observable Markov decision process (POMDP) related to the MAB problem [19]. In the rest of the paper, we will develop a particular MAB inspired RL algorithm for solving the complicated POMDP at hand.

III. PROPOSED METHOD

The proposed method is based on the Thompson sampling algorithm [22]. Thompson sampling is a Bayesian learning method that balances exploration (gathering more information about unknown parameters) and exploitation (maximizing current performance using existing knowledge of these parameters). This algorithm works in two stages. First, it uses Bayes' rule to update the posterior distribution of the unknown parameters. Second, it samples these parameters from the posterior distribution and solves the problem as if they were known. The unknown parameters in the considered problem include the target directions, target gains, and uncertainty regarding the number of targets. If those parameters are known, the best policy to solve (12) is the one that maximizes the sum of the GLRT PoDs while meeting the communications rate constraints.

A. Belief state update rule

We use a discretized grid of target kinematic states encoded in the range-Doppler-azimuth (RDA) data cube. Since the coherent processing interval (CPI) is expected to be short compared to the kinematics of the targets, we assume that targets move sufficiently slow between the RDA cells. Each RDA cell is indexed by $i \in \mathcal{I}$ which are associated with corresponding delay indices $i_{\tau} \in \{0, \dots, N-1\}$, Doppler indices $i_{\rho} \in \{0, \dots, M-1\}$, and azimuth angle indices $i_{\theta} \in \{0, \dots, L_{\text{R}}-1\}$. Furthermore, to facilitate DFT based processing, the delay, Doppler, and azimuth of each cell are defined as

$$\begin{cases} \tau_{i_{\tau}} = \frac{i_{\tau}}{N\Delta f} \\ \rho_{i_{\rho}} = \left(\frac{i_{\rho}}{M} - \frac{1}{2}\right) \frac{1}{T_{\text{o}}} \\ \theta_{i_{\theta}} = \arcsin \left[2 \frac{i_{\theta}}{L_{\text{R}}} - 1 \right]. \end{cases}$$

The cardinality of the index set is $|\mathcal{I}| \leq NML_{\text{R}}$, which means every possible combination of RDA states is not necessary to consider.³ Denote g_i as the gain of a hypothetical target in the cell $i \in \mathcal{I}$, and $\mathbf{g} \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{I}|}$ is the vector of all gain values. Note, $g_i = 0$ can be interpreted as no target is present in i^{th} cell. Let us also denote η_i as the GLRT statistic at the i^{th} cell, and vector $\boldsymbol{\eta} \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{I}|}$ comprises the statistics of all cells.

The belief state is the posterior over the vector \mathbf{g} . We conveniently defined the RDA cells such that the GLRT

³For example, this is useful when considering only CP limited range cells and Doppler limited ($\rho \leq 10\Delta f$) range rates in OFDM-based sensing system.

Algorithm 1: Posterior Update Algorithm

Input: Active cells \mathcal{I}_A , cells with a detection \mathcal{Z} **Output:** Updated set of active cells \mathcal{I}_A .

```
1 Initialize  $\mathcal{I}_R \leftarrow \emptyset, \mathcal{I}_N \leftarrow \emptyset;$ 
2 while  $\mathcal{Z} \neq \emptyset$  do
3   if  $\mathcal{I}_A \setminus \mathcal{I}_R \neq \emptyset$  then
4      $(i, i') \leftarrow \arg \min_{i \in \mathcal{Z}, i' \in \mathcal{I}_A \setminus \mathcal{I}_R} d(i, i');$ 
5     if  $d(i, i') < \epsilon$  then
6       Move posterior from cell  $i'$  to cell  $i;$ 
7        $\mathcal{I}_R \leftarrow \mathcal{I}_R \cup \{i'\};$ 
8     else
9       Initialize a new posterior to  $i$  using the
        posterior of inactive cells;
10    end
11  else
12     $i \leftarrow$  any value from  $\mathcal{Z};$ 
13    Initialize a new posterior to  $i$  using the posterior
        of inactive cells;
14  end
15  Update posterior of cell  $i$  using (15);
16   $\mathcal{Z} \leftarrow \mathcal{Z} \setminus \{i\};$ 
17   $\mathcal{I}_N \leftarrow \mathcal{I}_N \cup \{i\};$ 
18 end
19  $\mathcal{I}_A \leftarrow (\mathcal{I}_A \setminus \mathcal{I}_R) \cup \mathcal{I}_N;$ 
20 Update posterior for all inactive cells  $\mathcal{I} \setminus \mathcal{I}_A$  using (16);
```

statistics are ideally independent. In other words, we can write the likelihood of GLRT test statistics as

$$\Pr \{\boldsymbol{\eta} | \mathbf{g}\} = \prod_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \Pr \{\eta_i | g_i\} \quad (13)$$

where $\Pr \{\eta_i | g_i\}$ is defined in (7b). Furthermore, we define the prior distribution to be independent among the indices i such that

$$\Pr \{\mathbf{g} | \boldsymbol{\eta}\} \propto \prod_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \Pr \{g_i | \eta_i\} \quad (14)$$

where

$$\Pr \{g_i | \eta_i\} \propto \Pr \{\eta_i | g_i\} \Pr \{g_i\}. \quad (15)$$

This simplifies the posterior update process since it can be done in parallel for each cell i . Furthermore, by discretizing the set of possible values of g_i , posterior update in (15) can be done efficiently.⁴

Despite the convenient parallel update rule in (14), updating the posterior of all elements in \mathbf{g} is computationally demanding since it needs to be updated at every CPI. Also, this approach is subject to error when targets move between the RDA cells and not being precisely on the 3D grid points. To alleviate these problems, we propose an approach that makes the method more robust and computationally efficient using the GLRT detector. Furthermore, the GLRT detector results are pre-processed to remove uncertain detections caused by spectral leakage when targets are between the cells.⁵

⁴In numerical examples, we show a particular approach for the discretization.

⁵We use a peak-finding algorithm to filter detections.

We divide the RDA cells into active cells $\mathcal{I}_A \subseteq \mathcal{I}$ and inactive cells $\mathcal{I} \setminus \mathcal{I}_A$; typically, $|\mathcal{I}_A| \ll |\mathcal{I}|$. A cell is activated immediately when a detection occurs in an inactive cell. However, there are two ways of initializing the posterior of a newly activated cell. If the distance $d(i, i')$ (e.g., weighted Euclidean distance) between the detected cell i and an active cell i' is below a set threshold ϵ , we associate a detection to that particular active cell and move the posterior to the newly activated cell. Then, we can update the posterior using the update rule in (15). Otherwise, the cell is initialized with the posterior distribution of inactive cells. The posterior of inactive cells $\mathcal{I} \setminus \mathcal{I}_A$ are updated using

$$\Pr \{g_i | z_i = 0\} \propto (1 - P_d(\theta_{i_\theta}, g_i; \mathbf{X})) \Pr \{g_i\} \quad (16)$$

where z_i is the detection result in cell i . The computational benefit of this approach is realized when prior $\Pr \{g_i\} = \Pr \{g_{i'}\}$ for all i and i' where $i_\theta = i'_\theta$ such that only a single posterior update per azimuth cell is required to cover all inactive cells. Algorithm 1 shows a pseudo-code of the posterior update procedure. Lastly, activating too many cells can be computationally problematic, but we can mitigate this by monitoring the posterior distributions of active cells and deactivating those with low expected gain values.

B. Controller algorithm

We formulate a reward function and employ a structured optimization algorithm to optimize decisions conditioned on the learned belief state. This method uses the approximation $\mathbb{E} [P_d(\theta, \sigma_\alpha^2; \mathbf{X})] \approx \hat{P}_d(\theta, \sigma_\alpha^2; \mathbf{P})$ which can be written as

$$\hat{P}_d(\theta, \sigma_\alpha^2; \mathbf{P}) = P_{fa}^{\left(\mathbb{E}[C(\theta; \mathbf{X})] \frac{\sigma_\alpha^2}{\sigma_s^2} + 1\right)^{-1}} \quad (17)$$

where

$$\mathbb{E} [C(\theta; \mathbf{X})] = M \sum_{l=1}^L g_l(\theta) \sum_{k=0}^K \sum_{n=1}^N p_{n,l}^{(k)} \quad (18)$$

and $g_l(\theta) = |[\mathbf{U}^H \mathbf{u}_T(\theta)]_l|^2$. The optimization problem for the controller is formulated as

$$\arg \max_{\mathbf{P}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \hat{P}_d(\theta_{i_\theta}, g_i; \mathbf{P}) \quad (19a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{k=0}^K \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{l=1}^L p_{n,l}^{(k)} = P_{\text{tot}} \quad (19b)$$

$$p_{n,l}^{(k)} \geq 0, \forall k \in \{0, \dots, K\}, n, l \quad (19c)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^K p_{n,l}^{(k)} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n'=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^K p_{n',l}^{(k)}, \forall n, l \quad (19d)$$

$$\sum_{l=1}^L \mathbb{1}_{\{p_{n,l}^{(k)} > 0\}} \leq 1, \forall k \in \{1, \dots, K\}, n \quad (19e)$$

$$\mathcal{R}_k(\mathbf{G}; \mathbf{P}) \geq C_k, \forall k \in \{1, \dots, K\} \quad (19f)$$

where (19b) is the total power constraint, (19c) ensures positivity, (19d) is unit subcarrier power ratio (SPR) constraint (ratio between maximum power of a certain sub-carrier and average sub-carrier power) to control range ambiguities, (19e)

ensures at most a single data stream per user per sub-channel, and (19f) ensures the required data rate for each user.

To satisfy the constraints (19b)-(19d), we use the following transformation.

$$p_{n,l}^{(k)} = \frac{1}{N} [\xi(\mathbf{\Omega})]_{n,l}^{(k)} [\xi(\boldsymbol{\omega})]_l P_{\text{tot}} \quad (20)$$

where $\mathbf{\Omega} \in \mathbb{R}^{K \times N \times L}$ and $\boldsymbol{\omega} \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times 1}$ are the parameters to be optimized, and $\xi(\cdot)$ is a softmax function that operates on the first dimension of the input.⁶ Let us define a shorthand notation for the conversion from the transformed variables $\boldsymbol{\omega}$ and $\mathbf{\Omega}$ to the power allocation as $\mathbf{P} = f(\boldsymbol{\omega}, \mathbf{\Omega})$. Additionally, we propose a surrogate rate equation

$$\tilde{\mathcal{R}}_k(\mathbf{G}; \mathbf{P}) = \frac{1}{T_o} \sum_{n=1}^N \max_{l \in [L]} \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{g_{n,l}^{(k)} p_{n,l}^{(k)}}{\sum_{l' \neq l} g_{n,l'}^{(k)} p_{n,l'}^{(k)} + \sum_{k' \neq k} \sum_{l''=1}^L g_{n,l''}^{(k')} p_{n,l''}^{(k')} + \sigma_k^2} \right) \quad (21)$$

where the maximum operation takes the rate associated with the best beam and the power on the other beams may cause interference. The constraint (19e) is eliminated by replacing the rate equation in (19f) with (21). Using this reformulation, we can rewrite the optimization problem as

$$\arg \max_{\boldsymbol{\omega}, \mathbf{\Omega}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \hat{P}_d(\theta_{i_\theta}, g_i; f(\boldsymbol{\omega}, \mathbf{\Omega})) \quad (22a)$$

$$\tilde{\mathcal{R}}_k(\mathbf{G}; f(\boldsymbol{\omega}, \mathbf{\Omega})) \geq C_k, \forall k \in [K]. \quad (22b)$$

Finally, after solving the problem, we can move all the excess power on each frequency and beam resource (in other beams than the best one) to the auxiliary sensing signal $k = 0$.

It is necessary to solve this problem efficiently using, for example, first-order optimization algorithms. We propose solving (19) as an unconstrained minimization problem where the loss function can be written as

$$\mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\omega}, \mathbf{\Omega}; \mathbf{g}, \mathbf{G}) = - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \hat{P}_d(\theta_{i_\theta}, g_i; f(\boldsymbol{\omega}, \mathbf{\Omega})) + \sum_{k=1}^K \lambda_k \max[0, C_k - \tilde{\mathcal{R}}_k(\mathbf{G}; f(\boldsymbol{\omega}, \mathbf{\Omega}))] \quad (23)$$

where the latter part of the equation corresponds to the penalty of not satisfying the rate constraints, and $\lambda_k > 0$ for $k = 1, \dots, K$ is the weight for each constraint. The dimension of the sum over $i \in \mathcal{I}$ in (23) is not a problem since typically $g_i = 0$ for many i . Thus, the resulting unconstrained optimization problem can be solved efficiently using a first-order optimization algorithm such as AdaGrad [23]. In addition, computation time can be decreased by optimizing power allocation on RBs instead of subcarriers, where each RB combines multiple adjacent subcarriers. All the proposed methods apply to RB-based power allocation by changing the dimensions and replacing the channels with average channels.

⁶For example, $[\xi(\mathbf{\Omega})]_{n,l}^{(k)} = \exp([\mathbf{\Omega}]_{n,l}^{(k)}) / \sum_{k'=1}^K \exp([\mathbf{\Omega}]_{n,l}^{(k')})$.

Fig. 1: Base station (BS), user equipment (UE), and target positions.

IV. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

A. Simulation setup

The performance of the proposed resource allocation algorithm is evaluated in simulations over a sequence of time steps. The performance indicators we compare at each time instance are (i) sum of PoDs, and (ii) violation of the rate constraint. The regret in (12) is not used to evaluate the methods because the optimal resource allocation is unknown. However, the regret is related to the sum of PoDs, and achieving a large sum of PoDs fast indicates achieving small regret as well.

We compare the proposed ISAC algorithm to three different methods. One optimizes (23) by setting weights $\lambda_k = 0$ for $k = 1, \dots, K$. In other words, this is the sensing-only approach that does not take into account the communications constraints. Another variant is the communications-only approach that excludes the sum of PoDs of the loss in (23). This effectively shows the communications sub-system's performance when any of the resources are not explicitly optimized for sensing purposes. Furthermore, we compare our proposed method to an algorithm randomly dividing the power into different resources. Especially, we sample $\boldsymbol{\omega}$ and $\mathbf{\Omega}$ from i.i.d. unit normal distribution, and use the transformation $\mathbf{P} = f(\boldsymbol{\omega}, \mathbf{\Omega})$ explained in Section III-B to obtain the power allocation.

In Section III-A, we introduced a generic model for the belief state update. We implement the update in simulations using a discrete set of gain values $g_i \in \mathcal{S} \forall i \in \mathcal{I}$. The set \mathcal{S} comprises $|\mathcal{S}| = 16$ values labeled as $s_0 < s_1 < \dots < s_{|\mathcal{S}|-1}$. We set $s_0 = 0$, corresponding to no target present in a cell. Other values $s_j \in \mathcal{S} \setminus \{s_0\}$ are defined uniformly between the values $s_1 = g_{\min}$ and $s_{|\mathcal{S}|-1} = g_{\max}$ on a decibel scale. The value g_{\min} is set by computing the minimum target gain for which the target can be found with 0.15 PoD if the transmit beamformer is fully aligned to the target direction. The value $g_{\max} = g_{\min} + 10^{35/10}$ is set to guarantee wanted dynamic range of 35 dB. The prior distribution of g_i is defined as

TABLE I: Simulation parameters.

Description	Symbol	Value
# of subcarriers	N	1200
# of symbols	M	128
Carrier frequency	f_c	6.0 GHz
Sub-carrier spacing	Δf	15.0 kHz
Cyclic prefix	T_{cp}	16.7 μs
Total power	P_{tot}	30.0 dBm
Noise power (per carrier)	$\sigma^2, \sigma_k^2 \forall k \in [K]$	-132.2 dBm
# of TX/RX antennas	L_T, L_R	32
RB size		12
Rate requirement	$C_k \forall k \in [K]$	19.8 Mbps
# of targets	Q	8
Mean RCS	σ_{rcs}	1.0
# of users	K	4
# of Monte Carlo iterations		80
Prob. of False Alarm	P_{fa}	1.0e-06

TABLE II: Sensing properties of the considered ISAC system.

Unambiguous range	9.99 km
Max range (CP limited)	2.50 km
Range resolution	8.33 m
Unambiguous range rate	539.41 km/h
Max range rate (Doppler limited)	269.81 km/h
Range rate resolution	4.21 km/h
Integration time	10.67 ms

follows. The probability $\Pr\{g_i = s_0\}$ should be a large value since it resembles the prior probability that a target is absent from a particular cell. We define it using the prior expected number of targets in the scene $\hat{Q} = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} 1 - \Pr\{g_i = s_0\}$ such that $\Pr\{g_i = s_0\} = \hat{Q}/|\mathcal{I}|$ for all $i \in \mathcal{I}$. In simulations, we use $\hat{Q} = 128$ (i.e., 4 targets per beam), and $\Pr\{g_i = s_j\} = (1 - \Pr\{g_i = s_0\})/(|\mathcal{S}|-1)$ for all $j > 0$ and $i \in \mathcal{I}$.

The locations of the BS, UEs, and targets are shown in Fig. 1. For clarity, UEs do not contribute as targets, meaning their radar cross section (RCS) is zero. We define the target signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) as $MP_{tot}\sigma_\alpha^2/\sigma^2$, where integration is taken into account and σ^2 is the per subcarrier noise power while total noise power is $N\sigma^2$. A standard monostatic radar equation is used for the SNR such that we define the target gain as

$$\sigma_{\alpha_q}^2 = \frac{L_T L_R \sigma_{rcs}}{(4\pi)^3 (\frac{r_q}{2})^4 c^2 f_c^2} \quad (24)$$

where c is the speed of light, f_c is the carrier frequency, and σ_{rcs} is the mean RCS of the target (all targets have the same RCS). With the parameters defined in Table I, the target SNR (with integration) varies from 19.93 dB to 32.48 dB when a single beam is pointed exactly at the target direction. The key sensing properties of the considered ISAC system are summarized in Table II. Note, the processing considers only the target ranges below CP limited maximum range and range rates below Doppler limited maximum range rate (defined in Table II), affecting the index set \mathcal{I} .

For the communications, we use line of sight (LoS) channel model

$$\mathbf{h}_n^{(k)} = \beta_k \mathbf{u}_T(\phi_k) \quad (25)$$

where β_k is the channel complex gain, and ϕ_k is the LoS angle to the UE. The channel is Rayleigh fading channel such that

(a) Sum probability of detection.

(b) Minimum rate.

Fig. 2: The proposed ISAC method outperforms the communications-only approach in sensing, with minimal loss compared to sensing-only. The solid line shows median performance, and the shaded area represents the 10th and 90th percentiles from Monte Carlo runs.

β_k is sampled from zero-mean complex Gaussian distribution with variance $\sigma_{\beta_k}^2$. Using the free-space path loss model, the average gain of the channel is defined as

$$\sigma_{\beta_k}^2 = L_T \left(\frac{c}{4\pi f_c d_k} \right)^2 \quad (26)$$

where d_k is the user distance from the base station. Communications SNR $P_{tot}\sigma_{\beta_k}^2/(\sigma^2 N)$ varies from 34.39 dB to 43.63 dB. This high communications SNR means that the communications rate is primarily limited by mutual interference.

B. Results

Fig. 2a illustrates the sum of PoDs over time for various methods. The proposed ISAC method consistently achieves a high sum PoD, outperforming the communications-only approach and closely matching the sensing-only method. This indicates that optimizing sensing resources is crucial. Integrating sensing and communications functions will degrade sensing performance, but the tradeoff is not too severe. Closed-loop methods (ISAC and sensing-only) significantly outperform the random baseline.

Fig. 2b depicts the minimum communication rate over time for different methods. The ISAC and communications-only

Fig. 3: Beampattern of the proposed method at the end of the simulation. Beams are directed and power allocated towards the targets and UEs.

methods consistently meet the 19.8 Mbps rate requirement for all users, whereas the sensing-only and random methods fail to do so. This demonstrates that the proposed ISAC method reliably provides the necessary communication rates while maintaining high sensing performance.

The optimized beampattern at the end of the simulation is shown in Fig. 3. Beams are allocated to all UEs and all targets except one. The target that does not receive any power is the one farthest away. Allocating power for it would decrease the sum of PoDs. Additionally, a beam at 0.523 radians is due to the exploration in Thompson sampling.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper proposes an RL algorithm for closed-loop spatial (beam-space) and frequency (subcarrier/resource block) resource allocation in MIMO-OFDM ISAC systems. The proposed method efficiently balances the tradeoff between sensing and communication tasks and addresses the exploration and exploitation problem by leveraging the Thompson sampling algorithm. We focus on target detection under constraints on data rates for communications users. The method achieves superior target detection performance and meets the communication rate requirements for UEs. The proposed method offers an attractive solution for joint sensing and communications in the emerging 6G systems in terms of adaptability and ensuring desired performance in dynamic and densely used radio environments.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Liu, Y. Cui, C. Masouros, J. Xu, T. X. Han, Y. C. Eldar, and S. Buzzi, "Integrated sensing and communications: Toward dual-functional wireless networks for 6G and beyond," *IEEE J. on Sel. Areas in Comms.*, vol. 40, no. 6, pp. 1728–1767, 2022.
- [2] M. S. Greco, F. Gini, P. Stinco, and K. Bell, "Cognitive radars: On the road to reality: Progress thus far and possibilities for the future," *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, vol. 35, no. 4, pp. 112–125, 2018.
- [3] M. Bica and V. Koivunen, "Radar waveform optimization for target parameter estimation in cooperative radar-communications systems," *IEEE Trans. on Aerosp. and Electron. Syst.*, vol. 55, no. 5, pp. 2314–2326, 2019.

- [4] M. Bica and V. Koivunen, "Multicarrier radar-communications waveform design for RF convergence and coexistence," in *IEEE Int. Conf. on Acoust., Speech and Signal Process. (ICASSP19)*, pp. 7780–7784, 2019.
- [5] C. Shi, Y. Wang, F. Wang, and H. Li, "Joint optimization of subcarrier selection and power allocation for dual-functional radar-communications system," in *IEEE 11th Sensor Array and Multichannel Signal Process. Workshop (SAM20)*, pp. 1–5, 2020.
- [6] S. D. Liyanaarachchi, C. B. Barneto, T. Riihonen, and M. Valkama, "Joint OFDM waveform design for communications and sensing convergence," in *IEEE Int. Conf. on Comms. (ICC20)*, pp. 1–6, 2020.
- [7] A. Ahmed, Y. D. Zhang, and A. Hassanien, "Joint radar-communications exploiting optimized OFDM waveforms," *Remote Sensing*, vol. 13, no. 21, 2021.
- [8] X. Liu, T. Huang, N. Shlezinger, Y. Liu, J. Zhou, and Y. C. Eldar, "Joint transmit beamforming for multiuser MIMO communications and MIMO radar," *IEEE Trans. on Signal Process.*, vol. 68, pp. 3929–3944, 2020.
- [9] H. Hua, J. Xu, and T. X. Han, "Optimal transmit beamforming for integrated sensing and communication," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 72, no. 8, pp. 10588–10603, 2023.
- [10] Z. Wei, R. Yao, X. Yuan, H. Wu, Q. Zhang, and Z. Feng, "Precoding optimization for MIMO-OFDM integrated sensing and communication systems," *IEEE Transactions on Cognitive Communications and Networking*, pp. 1–1, 2024.
- [11] Y. Huo, C. Shan, Y. Ma, and H. Zhao, "Waveform design with detection probability maximization for MIMO-OFDM integrated sensing and communication system," in *2024 IEEE 99th Vehicular Technology Conference (VTC2024-Spring)*, pp. 1–5, 2024.
- [12] P. Wang, D. Han, Y. Cao, W. Ni, and D. Niyato, "Multi-objective optimization-based waveform design for multi-user and multi-target MIMO-ISAC systems," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 23, no. 10, pp. 15339–15352, 2024.
- [13] Z. Cheng, Z. He, and B. Liao, "Hybrid beamforming design for OFDM dual-function radar-communication system," *IEEE J. of Sel. Topics in Signal Process.*, vol. 15, no. 6, pp. 1455–1467, 2021.
- [14] N. T. Nguyen, N. Shlezinger, Y. C. Eldar, and M. Juntti, "Multiuser MIMO wideband joint communications and sensing system with sub-carrier allocation," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 71, pp. 2997–3013, 2023.
- [15] S. D. Liyanaarachchi, T. Riihonen, C. B. Barneto, and M. Valkama, "Joint MIMO communications and sensing with hybrid beamforming architecture and OFDM waveform optimization," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 1565–1580, 2024.
- [16] P. Pulkkinen and V. Koivunen, "Model-based online learning for active ISAC waveform optimization," *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing*, pp. 1–15, 2024.
- [17] R. S. Sutton and A. G. Barto, *Reinforcement Learning: An Introduction*. Cambridge, MA, USA: The MIT Press, 2nd ed., 2018.
- [18] P. Pulkkinen, M. Esfandiari, and V. Koivunen, "Cognitive beam-space algorithm for integrated sensing and communications," in *2024 IEEE Radar Conference (RadarConf24)*, pp. 1–6, 2024.
- [19] T. Lattimore and C. Szepesvari, *Bandit Algorithms*. Cambridge, MA, USA: Cambridge University Press, 2020.
- [20] J. Brady, N. Behdad, and A. M. Sayeed, "Beamspace MIMO for millimeter-wave communications: System architecture, modeling, analysis, and measurements," *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 61, no. 7, pp. 3814–3827, 2013.
- [21] C. Baquero Barneto, T. Riihonen, M. Turunen, L. Anttila, M. Fleischer, K. Stadius, J. Ryyanen, and M. Valkama, "Full-duplex OFDM radar with LTE and 5G NR waveforms: Challenges, solutions, and measurements," *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques*, vol. 67, no. 10, pp. 4042–4054, 2019.
- [22] D. J. Russo, B. Van Roy, A. Kazerouni, I. Osband, and Z. Wen, "A tutorial on Thompson sampling," *Found. Trends Mach. Learn.*, vol. 11, pp. 1–96, July 2018.
- [23] J. Duchi, E. Hazan, and Y. Singer, "Adaptive subgradient methods for online learning and stochastic optimization," *J. Mach. Learn. Res.*, vol. 12, pp. 2121–2159, 2011.